

Complex and chaotic magnetic fields and the nature of gravity

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Abstract: In traditional physics research, people regard electric field forces and gravity, as two completely different forces. However, after the study of the ternary equilibrium system through the law of ternary equilibrium, it is found that these two action forces actually have a certain correlation. And how are the electric field force and gravity formed? And what is the nature of these two acting forces? However, two problems are difficult to solve in the field of traditional physics. Today we will use this paper to reveal two problems difficult to solve in both traditional physics.

Key words: system; electromagnetic waves; electron; quantum mechanics; electric field force; electric field; magnetic field; electrostatic field; gravitational field; quark; basic particles

Introduction

In the law of ternary equilibrium and ternary equilibrium systems, we elaborate on the process of forming an electron of electromagnetic waves under the action of the ternary equilibrium law. However, electrons can also form more complex particles under the action of the ternary equilibrium law. And how does the electric field force acting between the charged particles form? This is one of the detailed analysis of this paper. In addition to the analysis of electric field force, the relationship between magnetic field force, electric field force and gravity.

1. How is the electric field force and the electrostatic field formed?

1.1 ternary balance system and electric field force

Through this paper, the Law of ternary equilibrium and ternary equilibrium system, in the interpretation of the ternary equilibrium system produced under the ternary equilibrium law, we know that electromagnetic waves and electrons are actually ternary equilibrium systems formed by the electromagnetic field under the action of the ternary equilibrium law.

Electrons are a more complex system relative to electromagnetic waves, and electrons are formed by two electromagnetic waves under the action of magnetic field force, forming a ternary equilibrium system with two system levels. According to the law of the ternary equilibrium system, when countless electrons are together, the combined force of the magnetic field force formed by two electromagnetic waves in the electrons forms a composite magnetic field force. This composite magnetic field force affects the motion trajectory between electrons. Under the action of the ternary equilibrium law, a certain number of electrons will eventually form a more complex ternary equilibrium system with three levels of three systems, the elementary particle system. With three system levels, the laws of motion between electrons are totalically complex

and chaotic. As if the trajectory of the chaotic pendulum is as elusive.

The force that drives the formation between electrons and electrons is a more complex magnetic system. Composite magnetic field force is the action force generated after the superposition of multiple magnetic field force, which is actually the electric field force between electron and electron.

But how to we further understand the electric field force between charged particles further through the ternary equilibrium system?

When several electrons are forming a stable ternary equilibrium system, then because the system has reached a stable state. When this system reaches a steady state, the system does not actively release electrons externally and internally absorb electrons, when the system exhibits no charge states externally. However, the electricity shown by the particles is actually judged by the attraction or exclusion of electrons, and the phenomenon of attracting and excluding electrons is, in fact, the more advanced system of electronic formation, which has not reached the basic characteristics when the most stability of the system.

When, in some particular case, the stable system suddenly loses an electron, then the system lacks an electron as a whole and becomes less stable. When the system lacks an electron, there is a positive charge. At this time, if there are other electrons all around this system, the magnetic field force generated by electrons in this system lacking an electron, it will attract a new electron to join, bringing the system to a more stable state. The system, which lacks an electron, then shows an appeal to the electronics.

Through the above series of interpretation of the force of the action between charged particles, we have probably been concluded that the electric field force is actually a kind of magnetic field force, the magnetic field force is called composite magnetic field force, the composite magnetic field attraction or exclusion, depends on the charged particle system (ternary equilibrium system) internal stability or not. Similarly, the electrostatic field forming the electric field force, in essence, is not an electric field in the real sense, but a composite magnetic field.

Often charged particles are actually some, with very complex ternary equilibrium systems with multi-level systems. And the charged particles are divided into many cases. Many particles formed directly by electrons (unstable particle systems) are charged particles themselves, and they carry many charges, and the real state is actually far more complex than that analyzed above.

1.2 Analysis of the quarks

We assume that when a number of electrons follow the ternary equilibrium law within a certain space, performing complex and seemingly disordered motions, they eventually form new ternary equilibrium systems (elementary particles). This eventually formed new ternary equilibrium system (elementary particles), probably because of some cardinality that the magnetic field force affects on the direction of the electric field, makes the formed new ternary equilibrium system (elementary particles) not a particularly stable system when the number of electrons is a certain integer. That is, the number of electrons in this new chaotic ternary equilibrium system (elementary particles) changes.

We imagine that if the electrons needed to form a most stable ternary equilibrium system

(elementary particles) are $n-1/3$, Because the electrons in the elementary particle (ternary equilibrium system) can only appear as integers, the actual number of electrons in the elementary particles (ternary equilibrium system) will be n or $n-1$, when the number of electrons is n , the elementary particles carry $1/3$ negative charges and $2/3$ positive charges when the number of the electrons is $n-1$.

We then continue to imagine that when $m-2/3$ electrons are together, a stable ternary equilibrium system (basic particles), then m or $m-1$ ternary equilibrium system (basic particles) appears, also with $2/3$ negative charges or $1/3$ positive charges. Similarly and so on, more similar situations, which is a quark.

Since there are multiple states between quarks and quarks, the charged situation of the higher-level ternary equilibrium system, including protons, atomic nuclei, etc., appears more changeable.

2.Gravitation and Chatic magnetic Field

2.1 Composite and Chatic magnetic fields

In addition to the magnetic force produced by a single magnetic field, the magnetic field force in a ternary equilibrium system can be roughly divided into two types, one called "compound magnetic field force" and one called "chaotic magnetic field force".

"Composite magnetic field" refers to the compound magnetic field formed by more than two magnetic fields interacting. "Composite magnetic field force" also refers to the joint force formed by more than two magnetic field forces, and this resultant force is called the compound magnetic field force. The most common compound magnetic field force in nature is "electric field force", and the most common compound magnetic field is "electrostatic field".

So what kind of magnetic field force is the "chaotic magnetic field force"? The formation of a chaotic magnetic field force first requires a chaotic magnetic field, so what is a chaotic magnetic field? The chaotic magnetic field is actually the superposition magnetic field of countless magnetic fields, which is both a superposition of disorder, but also an infinite number of magnetic fields.

2.2 Chaos magnetic field

Through the previous explanation, we know that electrons formed by electromagnetic waves can form more complex elementary particles, and that electrons and these elementary particles can form proton, neutrons, atoms, molecules, etc. These particles again form matter through a series of combinations. So in matter ultimately, it is a huge and chaotic ternary equilibrium system formed by electromagnetic waves following the law of ternary equilibrium. The movement of electromagnetic waves in the interior of matter is the movement of infinite superimposed chaotic states.

The infinite superposition of electromagnetic waves means that at the same time, countless electromagnetic waves will affect and move in various directions in each direction.

物体中两个相反方向运动的电磁波

Schematic diagram, is a hypothetical case. It is assumed that the superposition of two opposite directions of countless electromagnetic waves (which will persist in all locations and in the microscopic interior of the object).

If we assume that the two electromagnetic waves are a stationary state, and that their positions are completely superimposed together, all the conditions are identical, only in the opposite direction. What is their magnetic field? It will be completely superimposed together, but the completely opposite direction, the opposite direction is completely offset, and the compound magnetic field they form is equivalent to no magnetic field.

But if all conditions are consistent with the above, the only difference is that the positions of the two electromagnetic waves are not completely superimposed together, but a little distance (the true state of the micro world is equally impossible to be completely superimposed together). So what is their magnetic field? It is partially superimposed together, because the position of the two electromagnetic waves is not completely superimposed. The same will be mostly offset because of the opposite direction.

As in the macroscopic world, two straight, opposite forces act on the same object, the two forces cancel each other. But if the two forces in the opposite direction are not in a straight line, the two forces can not be completely offset.

Two forces that are not on a straight line will cause a certain change in the position of the object. Similarly, the two positions are not completely superimposed together on the electromagnetic waves, which will also produce some special effect. The superposition of the states of such countless magnetic fields is the chaotic magnetic field.

2.3 Chaos Field and Gravitation

Chaos chaotic magnetic field is a magnetic field infinitely superimposed from all positions, in all directions. When the magnetic field is superimposed by this infinite kind, the resulting chaotic magnetic field force formed is actually the gravitational force between objects, so the gravitational field is actually a kind of chaotic magnetic field. All objects are a complex system formed by electromagnetic fields under the law of ternary equilibrium, forming the action force of electrons, which is the simplest magnetic field force. The acting force of such systems as forming particles is the composite magnetic field force (electric field force). The formation of the force of the system in the universe is a chaotic magnetic force (gravity).

2.4 Natural phenomena derived by Chaotic Magnetic Field Theory

Although derived by the ternary equilibrium theory, the chaotic magnetic field is the gravitational field. So how can its conclusions be justified? We will imagine the object in the ternary equilibrium theory as a superposition state in the space of countless electromagnetic waves. We imagine what changes will happen to the chaotic magnetic fields generated when countless electromagnetic waves move?

Because the magnetic field force only has an effect on changing the direction of the electric field propagation. And the propagation speed of electromagnetic waves, we temporarily call it "absolute speed". "Absolute velocity" is the absolutely constant velocity of electromagnetic waves in the "absolutely stationary space" (similar to the concept of the ether). The concept of "absolute velocity" is close to the conventional physics concept of the speed of light, but slightly different, because the "absolute velocity" is the displacement of electromagnetic waves in absolute stationary space. The speed of light in traditional physics is also known about the displacement of electromagnetic waves relative to the meter in a unit of time.

Because the traditional physicists found in measurements of the speed of light, the measured light source was found to be the same whether close to Earth at extremely high speeds or away from Earth at extremely high speeds. So Einstein finally came to the wrong conclusion that time was relative to speed.

The measurement of the speed of light as the speed of light is because the earth where scientists measure the speed of light is a relatively stationary (or relatively low speed) object and has methods for measuring the speed of light. And the "absolute speed" light, is the absolute speed relative to the absolute stationary cosmic space, this speed will not change by the movement of the measured object, so anyway the speed of light is measured is unchanged.

In traditional methods of measuring the speed of light, the light is reflected back and forth by the mirror and then measures the speed by turning the middle gear. However, the movement speed of the ball where the meter is located is actually superimposed with the speed of light. The speed of light superimposed is offset by the light moving back and forth reflected by the mirror. That is to say, in the reflection of the mirror, one with the speed of the earth, and the other with the speed of the earth's motion. So, this method of light speed measurement actually measures the "absolute speed", not the speed of the light relative to the meter.

In fact, this measured speed of light constant phenomenon, with the theory of "absolute speed of light" constant, can actually well explain the reason for this situation. That is, the Earth where scientists measure the speed of light is a relatively stationary (or relatively low-speed rotation) object. The absolute speed of light, is the absolute speed relative to the absolute stationary cosmic space, will not change by the movement of the measured objects, so no matter how to measure the light of objects away from or near the earth, the measured speed of light is unchanged.

To summarize in a paragraph, any speed of the light source is superimposed with the speed of light (absolute speed), and the measurement is always the "absolute speed" (speed of light) of the light. But when superimposed with the speed of the meter, the measurement does not necessarily equal the speed of light (300,000 km / s).

This conclusion is actually close to the nineteenth century "ether theory", but at the end of the 19th century was falsified by the physical theory of that time, but can not be used to prove that ether exists, but can prove the correctness of the electromagnetic wave theory model (see the Law of ternary balance for details).

The movement in the macro world is just a relative displacement movement, which is actually a result of changing the established propagation direction of the chaotic electric field in the absolute static space. Because this magnetic field force

changing the direction of electric field propagation is a superposition change, the macroworld object motion.

Second, due to the "absolute speed" of the internal electromagnetic wave versus the absolute static space, relative to the moving object itself, the electromagnetic waves inside the object must still be moved according to the established movement trajectory of the three-way balance system, in order to maintain its system stability, so it will change the relative speed of the electromagnetic wave inside the object relative to the object. Because the relative velocity of the electromagnetic waves inside the object is changed, all the electric field waves moving in different directions change the time staying in each direction, and the effect of enhancing or weakening the magnetic field in some direction, which will eventually form a corresponding magnetic field generated by the movement relative to the absolute static space.

当物体产生相对运动时，对于参照物而言，相对运动的物体内部的电磁场会发生相应的改变，物体内部的电磁场发生相对改变，就会导致混沌磁场的相对改变，使物体呈现出类似于电子运动时产生的磁场状态。

This part of the electromagnetic wave with the same direction of the internal electromagnetic wave and the same direction of the object movement, relative to the object itself, the electromagnetic wave will slow, slow electromagnetic wave corresponding stay time in this direction will increase, the result of the increased stay time is the enhancement of the magnetic field. The electromagnetic wave in the opposite direction reduces the stay time in the opposite direction, and the stay time of the electromagnetic wave decreases as the result of the weakened magnetic field. The series of analyses conclude that the movement of an object relative to the absolute stationary space leads to regular changes in the object's chaotic magnetic field. The result of the regular change is that the moving object presents the state of a magnetic field.

3. Conclusion

All objects are a complex system formed by electromagnetic fields under the law of ternary

equilibrium, forming the action force of electrons, which is the simplest magnetic field force. The acting force of such systems as forming particles is the composite magnetic field force (electric field force). The system of celestial operation in the universe is a chaotic magnetic force (gravity). If the force between the cosmic objects is chaotic, the chaotic magnetic field produces a relative magnetic field caused by the motion relative to the absolute stationary space, which forms a relative magnetic field force. By relative magnetic field force through the movement of celestial bodies, it can actually solve some strange phenomena in the universe. For example, why are most of the planetary orbital orbits in the same direction? Why do most of these planets orbit orbit in the same plane? And to solve the mystery of the outer galaxy celestial bodies turning too fast! Solve the mystery of dark matter and dark energy! Wait for everything.

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